

Fatigue crack growth of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under variable amplitude loading

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Abstracts

In this paper, fatigue crack growth of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates loaded in variable amplitude was studied. Unidirectional Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates utilized in this work were prepared by hot press method. The retardation phenomenon of fatigue crack growth was discovered in Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under variable amplitude loading. Moreover, specimens were chemically etched to obtain the final delamination shapes after application of single overload, multiple overload and block overload, respectively. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) was used to analyze the crack initiation position and the delamination. Furthermore, the fatigue crack growth mechanism was revealed according to the SEM results.

Key words: fatigue crack; Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates; amplitude loading

1. Introduction

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs), composed by thin metal layers and fiber reinforced resin layers, are widely recognized for its excellent fatigue properties and high damage tolerance^[1]. By changing its structures or materials to optimize the properties, FMLs has experienced the development of four generations, becoming one of the hot research throughout the world^[2,3]. TiGr (Titanium/Graphite Hybrid Laminates) was the fourth generation of FMLs developed by University of Illinois^[4]. TiGr not only maintains the high specific strength, excellent fatigue and impact resistance, but also overcomes the problem of low stiffness of GLARE(Glass Reinforced Aluminum Laminates) and electrochemical etching of CARLL(Carbon Reinforced Aluminum Laminates)^[5].

Due to the existence of fiber reinforced layer, the fiber metal laminates have excellent anti fatigue performance. Actually, compared to constant amplitude (CA) loading, most of the airplane structures are subjected to variable amplitude (VA) loading which exists interaction phenomenon. Woerden^[6] studied on the fatigue crack growth rate of GLARE3-3/2-0.3 in different single overload conditions. The results showed that after

overload the retardation of GLARE increased with the increase of crack length. Plokker^[7] investigated the fatigue crack propagation behavior of GLARE3-4/3-0.3 laminates under variable amplitude loading, and then compared the predicted results with the experimental results. Overload caused the GLARE to exhibit retardation similar to that of metallic materials. Compared to the single overload, block overload will produce overload retardation effect more. However, the majority of researches^[8-10] for the fatigue properties of FMLs under amplitude loading concentrate on GLARE, it is also worth switching to the TiGr. As a result, design of FMLs for fatigue properties can be improved.

In this paper, Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates were alternatively laminated by titanium layers and carbon fiber reinforced PMR polyimide prepreps. The influences of single overload, multiple overload and block overload on the fatigue crack growth of the unidirectional Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates were studied in this work. The fatigue crack growth rate and the delamination between metal layer and fiber layer were investigated.

2. Experimental procedure

Figure 1. The curing process of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates

The PMR(Polymerization of Monomer Reactants) polyimide was obtained from Institute of Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Science. Carbon fiber used in this study was TR50S 6L provided by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd. The titanium was 0.3 mm thick layers of pure titanium (TA2) supported by BAOJI Titanium Industry Co., Ltd. Unidirectional Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates utilized in this work were prepared by hot press method. The optimized curing process was illustrated in Figure 1. Specimens were manufactured as a rectangle with center crack according to the standard ASTM E647 for the fatigue crack growth test. The fatigue crack growth process was observed real-time by the aigo digital microscope with a lens of sixty times, as shown in Figure 2. Moreover, specimens were chemically etched to obtain

the final delamination shapes after application of three kinds of overload. In order to study fatigue crack of the Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates, Scanning Electron Microscope(SEM) was used to analyze the crack initiation position and the layer delamination.

Figure 2. The experimental process of fatigue crack growth test

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 3 displays fatigue crack growth of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under the single overload of stress level of 160MPa and overload ratio of 1.4, 1.6 and 1.8, respectively. Fatigue crack growth retardation phenomenon can be viewed that the crack growth rate decreased after the overload. Meanwhile, the reduction range of crack growth rate and the zone size of crack growth retardation expanded as the overload ratio increased. The fatigue crack growth rate would return to the original level of stress when left the plastic zone of overload. In addition, the delamination pattern between titanium layers and unidirectional-pile carbon fiber prepregs of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under single overload can be seen from Figure.4. It presents that a certain bending phenomenon of delamination shapes near the overload areas.

Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7 indicate separately the effect of fatigue crack growth of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under multiple overload, high-low block overload and low-high block overload.

Figure 3. Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under single overload: crack growth rate vs. crack length

Figure 4. The delamination pattern of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under single overload

Figure 5. The effect to fatigue crack growth of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under multiple overload: (a) crack-length vs.number of cycles (b) crack growth rate vs.crack length

Figure 6. The effect to fatigue crack growth of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under high-low block overload: (a) crack-length vs.number of cycles (b) crack growth rate vs.crack length

Figure 7. The effect to fatigue crack growth of Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under low-high block overload: (a) crack-length vs.number of cycles (b) crack growth rate vs.crack length.

Figure.8 shows the SEM pictures of fatigue fracture in prefabricated notch of MT specimens. Figure 8 (a) is the SEM picture of all kinds of fracture distribution section. Figure 8 (b), Figure 8 (c), Figure 8 (d) and Figure 8 (e) are respectively the magnification SEM pictures of Figure.8a. Delamination and fatigue crack can be observed between titanium layers and unidirectional-pile carbon fiber prepregs near the fatigue fracture zone. Besides, carbon fibers remained intact while no fracture happened with the expansion of the fatigue crack in outer titanium layers. A periodic shear stress in the resin layer would take place under the stress transfer process and produce delamination, which has a direct relationship with the bridging stress of carbon fiber layer. There were a synergistic reaction and mutual restraint effect between crack in titanium layers and delamination, which can account for this procedure of the fatigue crack growth and the ultimate fatigue failure.

Figure 8. SEM pictures of fatigue fracture at prefabricated notch of MT specimens:

(a) SEM picture of all kinds of fracture distribution section; (b), (c), (d) and (e) are respectively the magnification SEM pictures of (a).

4. Conclusions

Within the limitations of this work, the following conclusions were obtained:

1. The retardation phenomenon of fatigue crack growth was discovered in Ti/Cf/PMR polyimide laminates under variable amplitude loading, resulting in the fatigue crack growth rate decreased.
2. Observed by chemical etching of outer titanium layer, a certain bending phenomenon of delamination shape near the overload areas was found.
3. According to the SEM pictures of fatigue fracture at prefabricated notch of MT specimens, a periodic shear stress in the resin layer will take place in the stress transfer process and produce delamination, which combined with the bridging effect of the carbon fibers, leading to the fatigue crack growth.

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